

STUDIES IN THE FIELD OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

Marjona Mukhammadjonova

Student of UZSWLU

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Abstract. *In this article, intercultural communication takes place in different forms, for example; planned negotiations, for example, between representatives of government agencies or business organizations of countries with different cultures; unplanned communication, for example, during travel, at conferences or academic seminars. In the second case, representatives of one culture try to stick together, and information is given about the harmonization of relations between two cultural groups.*

Key words: *Travel, conference, cuultural, methodolgy, communication, anthropological, sociological.*

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В ОБЛАСТИ МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОММУНИКАЦИИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье межкультурная коммуникация протекает в разных формах, например; запланированные переговоры, например, между представителями государственных органов или бизнес-организаций стран с разными культурами; незапланированное общение, например, во время путешествий, на конференциях или научных семинарах. Во втором случае представители одной культуры стараются держаться вместе, и дается информация о гармонизации отношений между двумя культурными группами.*

Ключевые слова: *Путешествие, конференция, культурология, методология, коммуникация, антропологическое, социологическое.*

Today, there are two main lines of research in intercultural communication. The first of them is based on folklore. Its tasks are to identify, describe and interpret the everyday behavior of people in order to explain the deep causes and determinants of culture.

The second direction, which has a cultural and anthropological nature, is the subject of his research. cultural activities of different types of social groups and communities, their norms, rules and values. The social differentiation of the society causes specific models and rules of behavior in each group. Knowing them allows you to quickly and effectively resolve cross-cultural misunderstandings.

The main tasks of research in the field of intercultural communication:

- ✓ definition of the subject, methodology and conceptual apparatus of intercultural communication;
- ✓ determining the place of intercultural communication among other disciplines;
- ✓ the ability to form and develop cultural sensitivity among the participants of intercultural dialogue, to correctly interpret the specific appearance of communicative behavior and a tolerant attitude towards it;
- ✓ developing a methodology for teaching practical skills and competencies in communication with representatives of other cultures.

Intercultural communication can be practiced and learned at the group level or at the individual level. In other words, it is possible to study communication processes between different cultural groups (large and small) or between individuals... Most of the research conducted at the

group level is of the nature of cultural-anthropological and sociological research, which considers a cultural group as a collective unit (whole) and tries to understand it as a whole.

Interpersonal level of communication. The ultimate subject of intercultural communication is the person himself. These are people who are in direct contact with each other. At the same time, willingly or unwillingly, these people are members of certain social groups with their own cultural characteristics. The behavior of each person is determined by the system of social relations and the culture included in it. Each participant of cultural communication has his own system of rules, but these rules are determined by his socio-cultural communication. The differences in these rules can be seen as the difference between verbal and non-verbal codes in the specific context of intercultural communication. Therefore, in direct communication, representatives of different cultures use not only linguistic barriers, but also non-linguistic nature and reflect the ethno-national and socio-cultural features of understanding the surrounding world. Features of thinking, different linguocultural communities have to overcome specific mimic and pantomimic (cynic) codes used by carriers.

Thus, it is known that the success or failure of communication mainly depends on whether the communication partners trust each other or not. This trust is primarily determined by two factors - a person's personality and his special knowledge. But these factors are relative across cultures. In non-Western cultures, [trust in one's personality is more important](#) than trust in one's own knowledge, while in Western cultures it is the other way around. Of course, this does not mean that all communicators in Western cultures are not reliable, and communicators in Eastern countries do not have the necessary knowledge. It is only in Western countries that special knowledge is more important than personal credibility, and in Eastern countries, credibility is more important than special knowledge.

And finally, it should be remembered that the process of communication and interpretation of messages in interpersonal communication is influenced by the age, gender, profession and social status of the communicator, in addition to cultural differences. They also leave traces about the nature of each concrete communication act and the degree of mutual understanding of its participants.

Intercultural communication in small groups is carried out in various forms: planned negotiations, for example, between representatives of state agencies or business organizations of countries with different cultures; unplanned communication, for example, during travel, at conferences or academic seminars. In the second case, representatives of one culture try to stick together and have to spend a lot of time and effort to harmonize the relationship between the two cultural groups.

Communication in a small group consisting of representatives of different cultures is effective only if its participants can adapt their communicative actions to the specific conditions of this group. Members of monocultural groups usually adhere to general group norms, while members of intercultural groups act as representatives of their own culture, and their specific values significantly influence the nature of communication. Anyone who has had to participate in such discussions or negotiations, from any culture, will say that they are offended when the discussion or proposals are contrary to their cultural values.

For effective communication in a small group, the communicator has to adapt to the cultural values and beliefs of other cultural group members. Often in an intercultural group, the

participants in the discussion show stereotypes about their culture not intentionally, but by force of habit, and their behavior, as well as the discussion process, is influenced by many cultural factors. Therefore, in situations where cultural values influence the nature of the discussion and the issues to be discussed, it is very important that the communication partners are aware and try to convince others.

This does not mean that the participants in the discussion should try to change their own cultural values or the cultural values of their partners and thus open the way to an agreement (experience shows that a culture whose representatives tend to blame their cultural values for their problems or 'q). On the contrary, it is more appropriate to solve problems so that no one goes beyond the boundaries of their own culture. Sometimes the cultural system does not allow the changes that reasonable projects and programs proposed during the debates dictate. In this case, it is better to try to find another practical solution that does not require a radical cultural change.

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